

Factors Related to Teachers' Analysis of Classroom Assessments

Authors : Hussain A. Alkharusi, Said S. Aldhafri, Hilal Z. Alnabhani, Muna Alkalbani

Abstract : Analysing classroom assessments is one of the responsibilities of the teacher. It aims improving teacher's instruction and assessment as well as student learning. The present study investigated factors that might explain variation in teachers' practices regarding analysis of classroom assessments. The factors considered in the investigation included gender, in-service assessment training, teaching load, teaching experience, knowledge in assessment, attitude towards quantitative aspects of assessment, and self-perceived competence in analysing assessments. Participants were 246 in-service teachers in Oman. Results of a stepwise multiple linear regression analysis revealed that self-perceived competence was the only significant factor explaining the variance in teachers' analysis of assessments. Implications for research and practice are discussed.

Keywords : analysis of assessment, classroom assessment, in-service teachers, self-competence

Conference Title : ICE 2014 : International Conference on Education

Conference Location : Barcelona, Spain

Conference Dates : February 27-28, 2014